

Working alliance as predictor of treatment outcomes in digital health interventions: a protocol for a systematic review

Jürgen Barth¹, Diana Buitrago-Garcia¹, Noelia Álvarez²,
Jesús López-Alcalde^{1,3,4*}, Claudia M. Witt^{1*}

* Both authors share role of senior authors

¹ Complementary and Integrative Digital Health, Institute of Primary Care, University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich, Switzerland

² Medical Library, Hospital Universitario Ramón y Cajal, Cochrane Madrid, Madrid, Spain

³ Faculty of Medicine, Universidad Francisco de Vitoria (UFV), Madrid, Spain

⁴ Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria (IRYCIS), Unidad de bioestadística clínica, Hospital Universitario Ramón y Cajal, (CIBERESP), Cochrane Madrid, Madrid, Spain.

Contact person: Jürgen Barth

juergen.barth@usz.ch

Complementary and Integrative Digital Health
Institute of Primary Care – University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich

Sonneggstrasse 6, 8091 Zurich, Switzerland

Phone +41 44 255 48 96

Date protocol completed

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Signature:

Dr. Jürgen Barth

1. Background

Digital therapeutics are defined as “health software intended to treat or alleviate a disease, disorder, condition, or injury by generating and delivering a medical intervention that has a demonstrable positive therapeutic impact on a patient’s health” ¹. Digital health interventions have become a promising approach for a broad range of health conditions, with users often having an active role in the treatment.

There are some baseline patient factors (like sex, digital health literacy) that may have an association with engagement with the digital health interventions and their effectiveness. Moreover, there are process measures that can be assessed during the intervention phase, such as the digital working alliance of a user with the digital health intervention, which were found to be associated with better treatment effects ²⁻⁴.

Working alliance an overarching construct that consists of three separate components ⁵: bond (feeling of being connected to the treatment), task (belief that the way the health symptoms are treated is beneficial), and goal (agreement on the overall goal of the treatment) can be measured in the context of digital health interventions, and has been defined as digital working alliance. In Digital working alliance can be seen as the relationship between a user and the digital health intervention. Digital working alliance reflects the similar concept as in face-to-face interventions with similar components. The initially developed scales for patients were adapted to fit with the digital health intervention or new scales were developed for this purpose ⁶.

Since previous systematic reviews with meta-analyses about the association of working alliance with treatment effects in digital health interventions restricted their study selection either to one specific disease (i.e., depression) or a specific setting (i.e., internet), this systematic review will broaden the scope, since many settings, health problems and interventions might be available where working alliance was investigated as a moderator of treatment effects.

2. Objectives of the review

- To assess the association of working alliance with changes in health outcomes (mental health, physical health, quality of life) in digital health interventions in any disease.
- To assess if different components of working alliance (bond, task, goal) have an association with changes in health outcomes (mental health, physical health, quality of life).
- To explore the role of the intensity of interaction in the digital health intervention (low vs. high interaction) as an effect modifier of the association of working alliance with changes in health outcomes.

3. Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

a. Types of studies

Design: We will include any prospective longitudinal study, independent of its design. To be eligible, the study must include a longitudinal measurement of health (baseline and follow-up) and a measurement of working alliance in between (i.e., before the end of the follow-up). Single-arm studies (pre-post measurement of health) will also be eligible.

We will exclude cross-sectional studies with an assessment of health and working alliance at the same time point. Randomized controlled trials using an interaction term of type of treatment and

working alliance in the statistical model will be excluded since it reflects the difference of the association of working alliance with the outcome between both active treatment conditions.

b. Types of participants

Adults: Study participants should be 18 years at minimum.

Health problem: We will not restrict the study population to a specific disease. Any physical or mental health problem should be present at baseline. These health problems can be diagnosed by a clinician or self-reported health problems assessed via a questionnaire by a patient.

We will exclude studies done on short-term health conditions (e.g., fever) and studies including the general population as the target population (e.g., public health interventions). Also, we will exclude studies with healthy subjects or with a mixed sample (general population) unless our target population (patients with health problems) represents more than 80% of the study sample.

c. Intervention

Digital health intervention: We will focus on studies where patients have an active role in using the intervention. These interventions can use patient education frameworks, new health behaviour can be acquired with the digital health intervention, or patients receive a digitally adapted intervention similar to an intervention in a face-to-face setting (e.g., cognitive behavioural therapy for depression), or patients practice specific exercises to manage symptoms (e.g., relaxation exercises). The minimum intensity of the intervention should be either four sessions or with a duration of four weeks since it can be assumed that building a working alliance to an intervention requires time after the start of the intervention and most digital health interventions have a least such an intensity ⁷.

Device: The digital health intervention can be delivered by computer, smartphone, tablet or a specific newly developed device.

We will exclude studies solely designed to track the health status (e.g., a device tracking blood glucose level to send this information to the patient or the treatment provider) without any active interaction with the digital health intervention or a specific treatment goal. Studies with digital tools solely measuring patient activities, biomarkers, etc. for monitoring purposes will be also excluded.

Studies where only parts of the whole intervention are provided in a digital way, whereas other parts are delivered face-to-face, will be excluded. Interventions based solely on short messages or remote communication (i.e., telehealth) with a health care professionals will also be excluded.

d. Types of predictors

We will include studies investigating the impact of working alliance as a predictor for treatment outcomes in digital health interventions.

Working alliance consists of three separate components ⁵: bond (feeling of being connected to the treatment), task (belief that the way the health symptoms are treated is beneficial), goal (agreement on the overall goal of the treatment). These components can be reported separately or as total score. For digital health interventions this concept was used as digital working alliance. Digital working alliance reflects the similar concept as in face-to-face interventions with similar components. However, the wording of the initially developed scales was adapted to fit with the digital health intervention or new scales were invented for this purpose ⁶. Despite the fact, that many different wordings are used (e.g., digital therapeutic alliance, digital therapeutic

relationship) for this systematic review we keep the term working alliance as the most general term.

Timepoints: Working alliance must be measured during the first half of the full intervention period in the respective study arm, since an early assessment avoids confounding with treatment success (i.e. outcome of the intervention).

Type of measure: The measure must be reported using a standardized and validated questionnaire for working alliance which can be regarded as a scale. Data about working alliance should be self-reported data by study participants and not observed or reported by proxies. Studies using single items for working alliance are excluded. In case of multiple time points for the assessment of working alliance, the first time point of the assessment will be the relevant one.

Dimensions of the measure: If subscales of working alliance are available (bond, task, goal), these associations and scores with the change in health will be also extracted in addition to the total score.

e. Type of outcomes to be predicted

Eligible outcomes will be any health outcome measured after the intervention, which will be grouped as follows:

1. Physical health outcomes
2. Mental health outcomes
3. Quality of life

If more than one prediction model with different health outcomes is presented, the data of the primary health outcome defined by the study team will be used.

Changes in health: A prediction of the treatment outcome with working alliance is only meaningful if the authors controlled the analyses for the baseline severity of health using linear regression models. Another approach is to use change scores in symptom severity between baseline and the outcome measurement in the analysis. Both approaches are eligible since they reflect a change in health.

Period over which the association is predicted: The time point of the working alliance assessment should be in the first half of the intervention period. The outcome is measured at the end of the intervention. Additional follow-up periods will not be considered.

Measurement: Outcomes are eligible if a standardized and validated outcome measure was used. The outcome can be self-reported or by an external observer.

Studies measuring outcomes that are not regarded as “health outcomes” will be excluded (i.e., satisfaction with intervention, adherence to intervention). Studies with solely biological markers (i.e., inflammation markers, blood glucose levels) as outcomes will be excluded.

Search methods for identification of studies

a. Electronic searches

We will search for eligible studies in the following databases: Medline-Ovid, Embase-Ovid, PsycINFO, CINAHL, LILACS, and Epistemonikos. We will search studies published from 2006 onward since a previous review on the topic identified the first published study on this specific topic in 2006⁸. The searches will be developed by an experienced information specialist and peer reviewed using the PRESS checklist⁶.

b. Searching other resources

We will screen the reference lists of included studies and published systematic reviews on working alliance in digital health interventions. We will use Google Scholar to identify additional studies that have cited included studies or available systematic reviews.

Data collection and analysis

a. Selection of studies

One reviewer will screen all titles and abstracts, and another reviewer will cross-check 20% of the excluded references. Two reviewers will independently assess full texts for inclusion according to pre-defined exclusion reasons. Any disagreements will be solved by consensus or by involving a third reviewer.

We will use the EPPI-Reviewer web-based software⁹ to implement the selection process. We will complete a PRISMA flow chart to describe the selection process¹⁰. If there are multiple reports of the same study or data sets that overlap, we will collate them so that each study (not each report), is the unit of interest in the review. We will extract data from the data set with the most detailed results.

b. Data extraction

Data extraction of study characteristics will be performed by one reviewer and cross-checked by another one after an intensive training based on a previously piloted extraction manual. The following data will be extracted:

- Dates, country, and setting in which the study was conducted
- Study design
- Participants' characteristics (age, sex, education, digital health literacy, country of residence, race)
- Diagnosis/health problem of study participants
- Digital health literacy
- Treatment details (duration, intensity of interaction)
- Device (computer, smartphone, etc.)
- Predictor (working alliance total, bond, task, goal)
- Outcome (physical health, mental health, Quality of Life)
- Presence of a valid registration for the analysis
- Type of analysis (baseline adjustment of symptom vs. change score of symptoms)
- Other variables used in the adjusted analysis
- Estimate of the correlation/predictor
- Co-variates used in the adjusted analysis
- Number of participants in the analysis and percentage of participants in the analysis compared to included participants

We will use the online EPPI-Reviewer software (Park 2018) to build the data extraction templates and extract the data. We will pilot the data extraction form with five studies for usability. We will summarize the information retrieved in a table detailing the characteristics of each included study.

c. Risk of bias assessment

We will use items from the QUIPS tool (Quality In Prognosis Studies)¹¹ to judge on risk of bias.

- 1) Study participation: We will evaluate if the included sample represents the population of interest. Important characteristics are education level, (digital) health literacy, etc., since such characteristics may increase working alliance in a digital health intervention. If the population does not reflect the population to be expected, we will judge the study as high risk for this dimension.
- 2) Attrition: Study participants may drop out from the intervention or the study if they are not convinced by the intervention, which might be associated with working alliance. If less than 80% of the initially included study participants are analyzed, this study will be judged as high risk for this dimension.
- 3) Prognostic factor measurement: We evaluate whether a valid and reliable questionnaire for working alliance was used. If this is not the case, the study will be judged as high risk.
- 4) Outcome measurement: Since a valid assessment instrument for the outcome is already an inclusion criterion, all studies will be rated as low risk.
- 5) Study confounding: Since we exclude studies using the health outcome after the intervention without controlling for baseline severity in the analysis, all studies are rated as low risk.
- 6) Statistical analysis and reporting: We will evaluate whether the statistical analysis was appropriate. If this is not the case, the study will be rated as high risk.

For the final rating of risk of bias, we will consider studies at high risk of bias if at least one of the dimensions is high risk.

d. Measure of working alliance association with outcome

Measure of association: The analysis of the association of working alliance with health must be presented as an analysis of the longitudinal association of working alliance and changes in health outcomes. It should be either correlations, regression coefficients, or any related statistics used for associations. Measures for dichotomous outcomes (Odds ratio, relative risk, etc.) will not be used. For the analysis of the relationship between working alliance and treatment outcome, the health outcome must be used as a scale and not transformed into categories (i.e., responder). Analyses adjusted for co-variables will be prioritized over non-adjusted analyses.

If a meta-analysis is conducted, we will stratify it by the intensity of the interaction between users and the digital health intervention. In a low interaction setup, study participants receive only feedback about their progress or set their own goals for self-care interventions. Studies with a high interaction setup mimic a face-to-face intervention (like chatbots).

This results in a maximum of 24 meta-analyses (4 predictors, 3 outcome domains, 2 levels of intensity of the interaction) (Table 1)

Table 1: Expected combinations of analyses by type of intervention and outcome

	Mental Health	Physical Health	Quality of Life
low interaction intervention	Predictor: Working Alliance total Bond / Task / Goal	Predictor: Working Alliance total Bond / Task / Goal	Predictor: Working Alliance total Bond / Task / Goal
high interaction intervention	Predictor: Working Alliance total Bond / Task / Goal	Predictor: Working Alliance total Bond / Task / Goal	Predictor: Working Alliance total Bond / Task / Goal

The association between working alliance and changes in treatment outcomes will be measured with correlations, standardized beta, or any equivalent statistics. All reported data will be

transformed into correlations (r), and the number of data points (number of subjects) must be reported. We will conduct a Fisher transformation of the correlation coefficients before conducting the meta-analysis.

$$z = .5[\ln(1+r) - \ln(1-r)]$$

If the same study presents different analyses for the same outcome, each using a different aspect of working alliance (bond, task, goal), estimates from all analyses will be extracted, but analysed separately (see Table 1).

Direction of the associations

Positive estimates will reflect a positive association of a stronger working alliance with an improvement in health.

Assessment of heterogeneity

Between-study heterogeneity may result from patient characteristics and methodological characteristics of the studies. We will conduct subgroup analyses to explore possible reasons for heterogeneity. We will also display the summary findings in a forest plot for a visual inspection of heterogeneity. τ^2 and I^2 will be used to inform about statistical heterogeneity.

Data synthesis

Descriptive findings across all studies will be presented in the text and in tables for extracted data. We will conduct a meta-analysis if at least 5 studies are present for each cell in Table 1. We present the results as forest plots with a pooled estimate and 95% confidence interval and 95% prediction interval, including statistics for heterogeneity (τ^2 and I^2). We will employ a random effects meta-analysis. We will combine studies in a meta-analysis independently of their risk of bias. The analysis will be conducted in Comprehensive Meta-Analysis and R software.

Subgroup analysis and investigation of heterogeneity

We plan to investigate whether the following prespecified factors can explain heterogeneity if there are at least 10 studies.

- Mean age of participants: less than 40 years versus older.
- Sex / Gender: female only vs. mixed vs. male only.
- Education level: More than 50% of the sample with higher education versus less.

Methodological factors

- Clinical diagnoses vs. self-reported symptoms for eligibility
- Time between working alliance measurement and outcome assessment (less than 4 weeks vs. 4 weeks or more)

Sensitivity analyses

We will assess the impact of risk of bias by excluding studies with a high risk of bias.

We will use a fixed-effect model after the random-effects model in the initial analysis.

4. Declarations of Interest

JB was involved in the translation of a questionnaire about working alliance into German language for face-to-face consultations. JB and CMW are at the moment part of a project validating a Digital Working Alliance scale. JLA, DGB, and NA: none declared. CMW: CMW has active research grants to the University for digital health projects from the Digitalization Initiative of the Zurich Higher Education Institutions, the Swiss National Science Foundation, the Swiss Cancer

Foundation, the German health care Innovation Fund, and Newsense Lab GmbH and has received honoraria from Swiss hospitals for scientific presentations on integrative oncology, digitalization and artificial intelligence in medicine.

5. Contributions of authors

JB: coordinating the protocol, reviewing search strategies, methodological input, writing the protocol, and editing the protocol.

DBG: methodological input, designing search strategies, and editing the protocol.

NA: designing search strategies, editing the protocol.

JLA: methodological input, editing the protocol.

CMW: methodological input, editing the protocol, funding.

6. References

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7. Appendices

Search strategy -Medline Ovid 1946 to January 26 2026

- 1 smartphone/
- 2 smartphon*.ti,ab.
- 3 (Mobile adj2 app*).ti,ab.
- 4 smart phon*. ti,ab {Including Related Terms}
- 5 Video Games/
- 6 Video gam*.ti,ab.
- 7 videogame.ti,ab.
- 8 Internet/
- 9 Internet.ti,ab.
- 10 Internet-Based Intervention/
- 11 (internet-based or web-based or online-based).ti,ab.
- 12 (internet adj2 intervention).ti,ab.
- 13 (email? or text* or SMS).ti,ab.
- 14 Cell Phone/
- 15 Cell phon*.ti,ab.
- 16 mobile phon*.ti,ab.
- 17 app*.ti,ab.
- 18 (m-health or mhealth or mobile health or e-health or ehealth).ti,ab.
- 19 (wearable* or activity track*).ti,ab.
- 20 conversational agent*.ti,ab.
- 21 Artificial Intelligence/
- 22 artificial intelligence.ti,ab.
- 23 AI.ti,ab.
- 24 Digital Health/
- 25 digital health.ti,ab.
- 26 Therapy, Computer-Assisted/
- 27 computer.ti,ab.
- 28 Digital Health/
- 29 digital health.ti,ab.

- 30 Telemedicine/
- 31 Telemedicine.ti,ab.
- 32 or/1-31
- 33 Therapeutic Alliance/
- 34 Therapeutic Allianc?.ti,ab.
- 35 (working adj2 alliance).ti,ab.
- 36 WAI.ti,ab.
- 37 Helping Alliance Questionnaire.ti,ab.
- 38 Kim Alliance Scale.ti,ab.
- 39 Therapeutic Alliance Quality Scale.ti,ab.
- 40 Therapeutic Alliance Scale.ti,ab
- 41 TAQS.ti,ab.
- 42 Therapeutic Relationship?.ti,ab.
- 43 Therapeutic bond?.ti,ab.
- 44 or/33-43
- 45 32 and 44
- 46 "Systematic Review"/
- 47 systematic review*.ti.
- 48 meta-analysis.ti.
- 49 metanalysis.ti.
- 50 scoping review.ti.
- 51 review.ti.
- 52 case report.ti.
- 53 expert opinion.ti.
- 54 delphi.ti.
- 55 Qualitative Research/
- 56 qualitative stud*.ti,ab.
- 57 retraction.ti.
- 58 or/46-57
- 59 45 not 58
- 60 limit 59 to yr="2006 -Current"